

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 1575 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-mayda ruxsat etildi.

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

“Zavur kollektor suvlarining kimyoviy tarkibi tahlili va ularni tozalash zarurati (Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi misolida)”.....	20
Kungiratbay Sharipov, Ma‘ruf Nurmanov	
Forming demand and stimulating sales in Uzbekistan.....	26
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Членство в ВТО как драйвер развития: взгляд Узбекистана через призму опыта Вьетнама и Казахстана.....	30
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Mamlakatimizda tizimli ahamiyatga molik banklarni aniqlash tartibi va ularning bank tizimi moliyaviy barqarorligiga ta’siri tahlili.....	37
Xolmamatov Farhodjon Kubaevich	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida aholi bandligini ta’minlashdagi dolzarb masalalar	44
Ibragimov Elmurod Gulboynor o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida elektr energiyasi ta’minoti hajmini yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmiga ta’sirini ekonometrik tahlil qilish.....	48
Fayziyev Rabim Alikulovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarining xizmat turlarini takomillashtirish amaliyoti	60
Umurzoqova Adiba Ochilovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi kooperativi boshqaruv tizimida buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	67
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
O‘zbekistonda qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlari umumiy hajmini prognozlashda ekonometrik modellar (yillik)	72
Qodirov Farxod Amirovich, Bo‘ribaeva Qundiz Muratbaevna	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari xavfsizligi tizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari.....	77
Mahamatova Maftuna	
Xufiyona va yashirin iqtisodiyotning amaliy tahlili o‘zbekiston miqyosida.....	83
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli	
Soliq tizimini barqarorligini belgilovchi omillar tahlili.....	87
Nurillayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad manbalarini mustahkamlash omillari.....	92
Soatova Nodira Boboxanovna	
Bank infratuzilmasining raqamli transformatsiyasi va resurslar bazasi shakllanishi: nazariy asoslar va texnologik yondashuvlar.....	97
Raxmatov Azizjon Jaloliddinovich, Jumayev Muzaffar Mahmud o‘g‘li	
Ichki auditning transformatsion potentsiali: tahliliy amallarni takomillashtirish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish.....	102
Misirov Akbarali Pardaboyevich, Ismoilov Asadbek Abdusamat o‘g‘li	
Xorijiy mamlakatlarda yashil moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo‘llari.....	110
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
Yashil moliya – iqtisodiy rivojlanish mexanizmi sifatida	117
Nodir Xidirov G‘iyosaliyevich	
Xo‘jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning likvidiligi va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta’minlashning xorij tajribasi va uning amaliy ahamiyati	122
Bauyetdinov M.J.	
Теоретические подходы к определениям агрессий социально - экономической и политической стабильности государства как фактор повышения рекреационных потребностей	128
Алимова Райхона Баходировна	
Innovatsion ta’lim texnologiyalari asosida talabalarning metodik tayyorgarligini shakllantirish.....	139
Komilov Umidjon Normurod o‘g‘li, Tulyaganova Gulnoza Olimjon qizi	

Kichik biznes subyektlarini moliyalashtirish manbalari	143
Nematulloev Suxrob Sobirovich	
“Sibir daryolarining burilishi” loyahasining tarixiy va retrospektiv tahlili	153
Mahmudov Nosir Mahmudovich	
Sarguzasht turizmini rivojlanishi va sarguzasht turlarda turistlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda instruktor-gidlarning roli	159
Tilovmurodov Dostonbek Furqat o'g'li	
Scientific-theoretical foundations of the use of ict in ensuring management efficiency and security in enterprises	165
Khalilov Bekzod Akhmatovich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit riskini boshqarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	171
Mirtursunova Dinara Anvarovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklarida masofaviy bank xizmatlarini joriy etishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	175
Tangriyev Izzat Raxmatullayevich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida eko va etno turizmni rivojlantirishning istiqbollari va iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	181
Erkayeva Barno, Xushvaqtoev Ramziddin	
O'zbekiston bank tizimida raqamli valyutalar va yashil investitsiyalar integratsiyasini takomillashtirish	186
Nodirov Azizxon Asrorovich	
Global energiya noaniqligining o'zgaruvchanligi ekonomertik modellari	192
Bezzod Qo'ziboev	
Экоцифра: цифровизация МСП для зеленого устойчивого роста	197
С.С. Убаева	
Qishloq xo'jaligini barqaror rivojlantirish va ekologik toza hududni yo'lga qo'yishning ahamiyati	201
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
Statistika fanining shakllanish bosqichlari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	206
Nabixodjaev Abbas Abdupattahovich, Umarova Mukaddas Abbasovna	
Hududlarning atmosferaga chiqaradigan zararli chiqindilar miqdorini sanoat mahsulotiga nisbati bo'yicha tahlili	210
Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich	
Qayta tiklanadigan vodorod narxlari strategiyasini o'rganish: xarajat noaniqliklarini bartaraf etish	216
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligini “yashil” iqtisodiyot asosida rivojlantirishga o'tishning zarurligi va mohiyati	221
Yoldoshev Mutalib Ibrohimovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda “yashil investitsiyalar” dan foydalanishning xorij tajribalari	225
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Rustamova Nasiba Arslanovna	
Ijtimoiy iqtisodiy ehtiyojlar va ularning iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi o'rni.....	230
Raxmonova Feruza Musaqulovna	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotda tutgan o'rni.....	234
Mirzaxajeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
Tijorat banklari muammoli kreditlarining likvidlikka ta'siri.....	240
Karshiyev Adham Anvarovich	
Kichik firmalarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning nazariy metodologik jihatlari.....	245
Ruzmetov Davron Ibrogimovich, Aliyev Maqsudbek Erkinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning moliyaviy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	251
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
“Deviant xulq-atvorli o'smirlarning ijtimoiy moslashuvining psixologik xususiyatlari”	255
Saidbekova Feruza Anvarbek qizi	
Aholi daromadlarini diversifikatsiya qilishda davlat siyosatining roli va imkoniyatlari	258
Nutfullayev Shohrux Mexli o'g'li, Qurbanov Ulug'bek Erkinovich	

Анализ показателей развития зелёной химии по всему миру и в узбекистане за последние десять лет.....	262
Фозилова Фирангиза Комиловна	
Tijorat banklarining o'zbekiston respublikasi iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri.....	270
Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich	
Biznes birlashuvda buxgalteriya hisobi va auditni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	273
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi, Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna, Mirzarayimov Sardorbek Ravshanovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida pul-kredit siyosatining maqsadi.....	277
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining ishlab chiqarish va bozorlararo aloqalarining statistik o'zgarish tendensiyalari.....	281
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
Iqtisodiy bilimlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishi.....	286
Po'latov Abdulloh Xolxo'jayevich	
Теоретические основы эффективного управления финансовыми ресурсами предприятий с государственной долей (на примере узбекистана).....	291
Ахмедов Дилшод Турсункулович	
Robototexnika asoslari va maktab ta'limida qo'llanilishi.....	298
Tuxliyev Muslimbek Sherzod o'g'li	
Sun'iy intellektlar yordamida o'quvchilarni hayotiy faoliyat ko'nikmasini shakllantirishi.....	303
Mirxasilova Zulfiya Kochkarovna, Abdurahmanova Ozoda Djo'rayevna, Kurbanov Azimjon Jo'raboy o'g'li	
Levi tengsizligi uchun A.N. Kolmogorov teoremlari.....	316
Saypiddinov Shukrullo Sadrdinovich, Baxramov Rustamjon Qambarali o'g'li	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar bank tizimida raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish afzalliklari.....	320
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich, Umedov Abdullo Umedovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasining mdh mamlakatlari bilan tashqi savdo faoliyati tahlili: o'zgarish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari.....	326
Ilyosov Asrorjon Axrorjon o'g'li, Abdullaev Alisher Maxmudovich, Tuxtasinova Muxayyo Mirzasultonovna	
Elektron tijoratni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	330
Madieva Zuxra Iskandarbekovna	
Inson resurslarini o'rganishning asosiy yondashuvlari: mohiyat-ta'rifiy tahlil.....	336
Bakirov Qobiljon Mamatyusupovich	
Bandlikni ta'minlashda davlat tomonidan institutsional muhit yaratishning roli.....	340
Dilorom Tojiboyeva, Umida Ravshanovna Anvarova	
Mamlakatimizda islom moliyasini rivojlantirish maqsad va choralari.....	346
Xoliyorov Xomid Boynazarovich	
Разработка экспертной системы для оценки финансового состояния предприятия.....	352
Tajibayeva Kizlargul Ajiniyazovna	
Farg'ona vodiysi viloyatlarida kichik biznes ko'rsatkichlarining o'zgarishi: panel regressiya tahlili.....	362
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarni hisoblashdagi asosiy muammolar va ularning yechimlari.....	368
Farmonov Ilhomjon Iqboljon o'g'li	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida korxonalar innovatsion faolligini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	374
Hakimova Nozimaxon Sobirjon qizi	
Mahalliy davlat hokimiyati organlarida milliy kadrlar zaxirasini shakllantirish.....	380
G'aniev Elyor Sobirjonovich	
O'zbekistonda sirkulyar iqtisodiyotga o'tishning ahamiyati.....	386
Mirzayev Muzaffar Maxmudovich	
The role of international investments in greening and ecological rehabilitation of the aral sea region.....	392
Osmanova Feruza Bazarbaevna	
“Зеленое направление” совершенствования бухгалтерского учета.....	397
Ибрагимов Гайратжон Артикович	

Xarajatlarni kelib chiqish joylari va javobgarlik markazlari bo'yicha hisobga olishni takomillashtirish.....	403
Xamidova S.Ya.	
Mintaqalarni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ularni takomillashtirish.....	409
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna	
O'zbekistonda kichik turar joy biznesini rivojlantirishda xorijiy tajribalar	414
Yo'ldashev Bekzodjon Sherzodjon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida davlat maqsadli dasturlarini moliyalashtirish yuzasidan ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	419
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o'g'li	
Qandolat mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	426
Azlarova Munira Muxammad-Amin qizi	
Risk management in commercial banks, methodological approaches and practical implementation	433
Baymuratova Zina Aqilbekovna, Jarilkapova Naubaxar Paraxat qizi	
The impact of competition on economic growth: evidence from uzbekistan's automotive industry.....	439
Saydaliyeva Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oliy talim xizmatlarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni.....	444
Mirzaxadjayeva Shahzoda Shuxratovna	
Развитие производства сельскохозяйственной продукции путем развития цифровых технологий.....	450
Юсупов Мухиддин Соатович	
Tijorat banklarida loyihaviy moliyalashtirish risklarini boshqarish amaliyotini takomillashtirish.....	457
Berdiyev Akram O'ktamovich	
Iqtisodiy tarmoqlarni soliqqa tortish orqali investitsiya loyihalarini rivojlantirish.....	463
Sharipov Eldor Salohiddin o'g'li	
Iqtisodiyotda investitsiya va kredit salohiyatini bank faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	468
Ergashova Nilufar Sobirovna	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining raqobatbardoshlik salohiyatini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	473
Tashmukhamedova Karima Samatovna	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va istiqbollari.....	479
Kurbanova Mohinur Xabib qizi	
Xalqaro sayohat lug'ati va uning shakllanishi.....	487
Abduaxadova Zilola Djamoliddinovna	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari va uni o'zbekiston respublikasi hisob tizimini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati.....	492
Quvvatov G'olibjon Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Kooperatsiyalarning tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati.....	501
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	
Использование методов математического моделирования при внедрении коммерческих автоматических систем	505
Курбанова Рахима, Ахмедов Мехрожон	
Tijorat banklari kapitalidagi davlat ulushini kamaytirish yo'llari.....	511
Vasiyev Alisher Samiyevich	
Механизмы трансформации неформального сектора в официальную экономику на основе финансовых инструментов.....	515
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Муртазаев Шахрух Коньсжайлиевич	
The impact of tourism on the economy of Uzbekistan.....	519
Xaydarova Marjona, Muxamedboyeva Muxlisa, Umarov Kamron, Usmanova Aziza	
Mintaqada gastroturizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy asoslari va zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	525
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	

Tikuv-trikotaj korxonalari brend jozibadorligini oshirishning ilmiy-nazariy jihatlarini.....	535
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
Bank tizimida hisobotlarni avtomatlashtirish texnologiyalari	542
Sodiqov Sanjar Saydullo o'g'li	
Engineering programs in Uzbekistan on the verge of fifth industrial revolution.....	547
Khasan Khankeldiyev	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining boshqaruvini yaxshilashda korporativ madaniyatning ahamiyati.....	551
Akramova Nazokat Israilovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatining iqtisodiy taraqqiyotdagi o'rni	562
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
O'zbekiston sanoat tarmoqlarida kooperatsiya asosida tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	572
Xalilova Sevaraxon Alijon qizi	
Moliyaviy barqarorlikning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari va ularning tahlili.....	578
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
Tijorat banklarining mamlakat iqtisodiyotida tutgan o'rnini tahlil qilish	583
Kilicheva F.B., Mengnorov A.A., Bozorova O.R.	
Bog'dorchilik tarmog'ida klasterlarni joriy qilishda yevropa tajribasini qo'llash imkoniyatlari	591
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
To'qimachilik klasterlarini boshqarishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	598
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Barriers to tourism infrastructure development in uzbekistan: a critical analysis	605
Sarvinoz Shodmonova	
Xalqaro bozorda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish	609
Mengnorov Almardon Abdirahmonovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishdagi risklarni boshqarish.....	620
Yusupova Zilola Ismoiljon qizi	
Korxonaning iqtisodiy barqarorligiga erishishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	626
Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna	
Qishloq joylari maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida axborot resurslaridan samarali foydalanish.....	631
Xamdamiy Eldor Toshtemirovich	
Meva-sabzavotlar eksportida transport koridorlari va vositalarini tanlash xususiyatlari.....	636
Yusupov Muxiddin Soatovich	
Рынок рабочей силы в узбекистане и ее воспроизводство	644
Шакиров Амали Улугбекович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Деньги и их функции в экономике.....	650
Мурадиллаев Мансур Мехроживич, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Развитие сельского хозяйства в узбекистане.....	654
Махмудов Алишер Мухтарович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Инвестиции и инновации в химической промышленности узбекистана: современные тенденции и перспективы.....	658
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович, Султанходжаев Аманулла Асадуллаевич	
Tijorat banklari aktivlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	666
Mardonova Shoxsanam Bahodirovna	
Definition of agritourism as a multifunctional development in rural areas.....	672
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani ugli	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvda smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumotlar bazasida shakllanishi	680
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullaevich	
Проблемы регулирования государственно-частного партнерства и рекомендации по их решению (на примере безработицы в республике узбекистан).....	687
С.Э. Холмуратов	
Автоматизация аудиторских процедур с использованием искусственного интеллекта.....	692
Ходжарахманова Назира Бахтияр кизи	
Past karbonli iqtisodiyotga o'tish zaruriyati va uning omillari.....	701
Valiyev Axliddin Aropitdinovich	

Yengil sanoatda zamonaviy tikuv mashina-kichik robotlarning mexanizmlarini mukammallashtirish	705
Sirojova Muxabbat Sodiq qizi, Kurbanov Fazliddin Aminovich	
Jismoniy shaxslar daromadlarini soliqqa tortish tizimining institutsional va iqtisodiy asoslari	710
Kuzieva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Bobomuratova Manzura Panji qizi	
Foyda solig'i bo'yicha bo'nak to'lovlarni to'lash tartibi	717
Yangieva N.S.	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliqlar vositasi qo'llab-quvvatlashning amaldagi holati	722
Turanboyev Boburjon Qodirjon o'g'li	
Motivation, goal-setting, and organizational performance: a case study from uzbekistan's chemical industry	726
Mamataliev Anvar Ergashevich, Bobur Urinov	
Применение искусственного интеллекта при организации налогового администрирования узбекистана	733
Н.А. Артиков	
Ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar	737
Sharofiddinova Gulnoza Iloxomjonovna	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning tijorat banklari samaradorligiga ta'siri	745
Maksudov Avazbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Suv tanqisligi sharoitida yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish asoslari	750
Qosimov Maxamatjon Sulaymanovich	
Rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotda raqamli va raqamli bo'lmagan korxonalar tahlili	761
Raxmonov Nodirjon Raxmonjon o'g'li	
Aholining o'rtacha umr ko'rish yoshini o'zgarishi sharoitida keksalarning ijtimoiy ta'minotiga xavflarning ortishi	767
Toyirov Shohboz Ziyodullo o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida moliyaviy nazorat samaradorligini ta'minlash ichki nazorat xizmatlari	773
Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich	
Moliya bozorida xususiy banklar faolligini ta'minlash istiqbollari	777
Abduqahhorov Asilbek Ahror o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlari ijrosini ta'minlashda soliqlar hisobi va tahlilining ahamiyati	782
Abdullaev Abror Bozarboevich	
Aholi daromadini oshirish yo'llari	803
Shadmanov Baxodir Sherkulovich	
Tourism and regional identity in Uzbekistan: balancing heritage and development	808
Raximova Nilufar Aminovna, Abdukholikova Farida Erkinjon qizi	
O'zbekiston sanoat korxonalarining fond bozorida ishtiroki tahlil va muammolari	815
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
O'zbekistonda davlat-xususiy sheriklik loyihalarini moliyalashtirish va amalga oshirish tahlili	823
Karabaev Sanjar Abdusamatovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida milliy korxonalarining eksport salohiyatini boshqarish masalalari	832
Qodirov Humoyun Tolibjon o'g'li	
Бизнес-планирование и прогнозирование деятельности организации	836
Алимов Бехзоджон Наврузжонович	
Farg'ona vodiysida ekoturizm – kambag'allikka qarshi kurashning yangi imkoniyatlari	840
Soliyeva Nilufar Muxtorjon qizi	
Aholi turmush darajasi baholash bo'yicha dasturiy ta'minot ishlab chiqishda horij tajribasini o'rganish	844
Tursunov Farxod Baxodir o'g'li	
Mintaqa aholi turmush farovonligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tasnifini ishlab chiqish	848
Xodjanibayozov Shohruh Yuldashovich	
Xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejmentining nazariy jihatlar va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	856
Karimov Ulug'bek Usmonovich	
Infratuzilma va bozor infratuzilmasi tushunchalarining nazariy tavsifi	861
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich	

Повышение инвестиционной привлекательности – важное условие повышения конкурентоспособности предприятий.....	865
Каримова Дилафруз Садирдин кизи	
Yevropa ittifoqi davlatlari tijorat banklarining soliq to'lovlarini amalga oshirish tartibi	870
Komolov Odiljon Sayfidinovich	
Boshqaruvda innovatsiyalarni hisobga olgan holda agrokorxonalarni davlat tomonidan rag'batlantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	878
Shaniyazova Zamira	
Практические аспекты применения статистических методов контроля качества на предприятиях.....	883
Усманов Илхом Ачилович, Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishning yangi paradigmalarini shakllantirish: nazariy asoslar va amaliy talqinlar.....	891
Alimova Guzal Abduxakimovna	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalari faoliyati samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarining nazariy va metodologik tahlili	895
Qo'ziboyev Boxodir Azzamboy o'g'li	
Kutubxonalarda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida biznes-modellarni ishlab chiqish.....	900
Ernaqulov Sunnatillo Nurali o'g'li	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri sug'urtalash operatsiyalari bo'yicha xarajatlarni xalqaro standartlar asosida hisob va hisobotda aks ettirish uslubi-yatini takomillashtirish	905
X.A.Raximov	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvida smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumotlar bazasida shakllanishi.....	910
Ergashev Uyg'un Jabborovich	
Obligatsiya moliya bozori instrumenti sifatida, milliy obligatsiyalar bozori	916
Avezov Ibrohim Iloxomovich, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdualimovich	
Barqaror rivojlanish doirasida ekologik, ijtimoiy va korporativ boshqaruv (ESG) ko'rsatkichlarining yashil texnologiyalar innovatsiyasiga ta'sirini baholash.....	921
Meliqo'zieva Dilrabo Muxitdin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot – barqaror taraqqiyotga olib boruvchi yo'l.....	925
Xalilova Aziza Rustamovna	
Научно-теоретические основы экономической и эколого-экономической эффективности предприятий горнодобывающей промышленности.....	930
Раматов Зафарбек Жуманиязович	
Xitoyda eksport faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	938
D.E.Qarshiev	
Kichik sanoat zonalarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirishni investitsion faollikka ta'siri.....	943
Mannapova Shaxnoza Elshodovna	
Mahalla institutining samaradorligi tahlili: so'rovnomaga yondashuvi	947
Bahriddinov Viqorjon Akbar o'g'li	
Формирование человеческого капитала в условиях демографических изменений: опыт и перспективы для узбекистана.....	955
Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи	
Farmasevtika kompaniyalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish yo'nalishlari	962
Вахромбек Бобоjonov	
“Hududlarda sug'urtaga bo'lgan talabning ekonometrik tahlili” bekberganova mohira ravshonbekovna	967
O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti	
O'zbekiston va xalqaro amaliyotda raqamli marketing vositalaridan foydalanish: muammolar va yechimlar	973
Uzoqova Dilnoza Yusuf qizi	
Условия эксплуатации и экологическая безопасность автотранспортной системы на основе энергосберегающих технологий	978
Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
O'zbekiston tibbiyot muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslardan foydalanishda xorijiy tajribalarni qo'llash.....	982
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	

Buxgalteriya hisobining samaradorligini oshirish yo'llarida zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalar	987
Sattorov Mirjahon	
Особенности маркетинговых стратегий в условиях ограниченных ресурсов и узкой потребительской аудитории	991
Дебердиев Анвар	
DEbitorlik va kreditorlik qarzlari auditini rejalashtirish masalalari.....	995
Tulovov Erkinjon To'liqin o'g'li, Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi	
Инвестиционная программа узбекистана по привлечению иностранных инвестиций	1000
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна, Бекмуратов Шухрат Даулетмуратович	
Turistik mahsulotni shakllantirishda turistlar hayoti xavfsizligini ta'minlash.....	1005
Rahmonov Siyovush Turob o'g'li	
Uglerodsiz energiyaga o'tishda o'zbekistonning yashil strategiya yo'l xaritasining integratsiyasi va ta'siri.....	1011
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Цифровая устойчивость регионов: применение аналитики больших данных для оценки и управления экологическими рисками	1016
Маликов Шохрух Шокирович, Камалов Шухрат Камалович	
Разработка риск-ориентированной модели внутреннего контроля предприятия на этапе планирования налогов в условиях дистанционного налогового мониторинга	1024
Галеева Н.Н., Э.А.Халикова, Абдусаломова Гулчеҳра Мирзо қизи	
Анализ результатов инструментальных методов исследований у детей с врожденными пороками сердца	1029
Мухаммадиева Лола Атамуратовна	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda monetar omillardan samarali foydalanish yo'nalishlari.....	1036
Uskenbaeva Dilnoza Voxodir qizi	
Факторы повышения эффективности управления в государственном секторе.....	1043
Махмудова Севара Улугбековна	
Soliq organlari va soliq to'lovchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning yangi tizimi sharoitida soliq nazorati	1048
Rajabbaeva Dildora Zakirovna, Aripova Aziza Alisherovna	
Boshqaruv jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	1053
Jo'rayeva Niginaxonim Xursand qizi	
Jahonda eksportni qo'llab-quvvatlash amaliyoti.....	1057
Xudoynazarov Sherzod Ismoilovich	
Raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni korxonada darajasida joriy etish orqali moliyaviy barqarorlikka erishish strategiyasi	1063
Soibov Nozimbek Faxridin o'g'li	
Применение методов PMBOK в управлении рисками проектов	1070
Гулираъно Носирова Абдулазиз қизи	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda aholi farovonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	1073
Bobaev Isroiljon Abdinabievich	
Вопросы инновационных инвестиций в контексте международной экономической интеграции	1078
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari hamda tendensiyalari.....	1083
Samiyev Abdurashid Qaxramonovich, Shermuxammedov Begzodjon Usmonovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar samaradorligini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	1087
Nazarov Qilich Xolmuradovich	
Improving the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of tourism in the republic of karakalpakstan	1092
Tleumuratov Baxadir Genjemuratovich	
O'zbekistonda tumanlar barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash yo'llari (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	1097
Qosimova Nodira Saidovna	
Innovatsion iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishning asosi sifatida innovatsiyalar.....	1102
Azizova Maliha Farrux qizi	

Влияние инвестиций на инновационное развитие и повышение конкурентоспособности экономики узбекистана	1106
Максудова Шахзода	
Возможности снижения затрат на логистику за счет цифровых технологий.....	1112
Олимова Бахора Шухратовна	
Yashil texnologiyalar va ularning iqtisodiy tizimga ta'siri.....	1116
Sultonov Omon Juma o'g'li	
Iqtisodiy o'sishning makroiqtisodiy faktorlari va ularning ta'siri	1121
Zuvaydullaev Nematullo Oybek o'g'li	
Роль управления производством в условиях модернизации экономики.....	1125
Гулов Мухтор Очилович	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati	1129
To'rayev Shavkat Shuxratovich	
Роль цифрового маркетинга в продвижении туристических направлений.....	1136
Муродова Наргиза Уткировна	
Развитие финансовых рынков в странах снг: проблемы и перспективы.....	1140
Рузиев Зафар Икрамович, Каримов Ислон Ураз угли	
Современные инструменты продвижения бренда в условиях цифровой экономики.....	1145
Темирова Феруза Сагдуллаевна	
“Raqamli asrda axborot xavfsizligi: it texnologiyalar bilan xavfsizlikni ta'minlash yo'llari”	1149
Sherzod Rajabov	
Государственное регулирование инвестиционной деятельности: проблемы и направления совершенствования.....	1152
Шухрат Турсунов, Икромов Хасан Зафарович	
Economic incentives and barriers to sustainable transition in agribusiness: a comparative study of organic and conventional farming systems	1157
Mubina Toirova	
Цифровая трансформация банковской системы узбекистана: анализ внедрения fintech-решений в государственных банках	1162
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Ta'lim muassasalaridagi ba'zi jihatlar	1167
A'zam Qutbiddin A'zam-zoda	
Klasterlar hisob siyosatida boshqaruv hisobining metodologik asoslari.....	1173
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Egri soliqlarning mohiyati, genezisi va rivojlanish tendensiyalariga oid nazariy munozaralar xususida	1179
Shodiyev Olimjon Abduraxmonovich	
Ekologik mehmonhona faoliyatini rejalashtirish maqsadlari va vazifalari	1186
Abidova Dilfuza Igamberdievna	
Investitsiya loyihalarining iqtisodiy va moliyaviy samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1200
Jo'rabekova Xumora Muzaffar qizi, Saidov Rasul Boltabayevich	
O'zbekistonda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarini moliyalashtirish manbalarining tahlili.....	1204
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini statistik tahlil qilish.....	1213
Jumanova Zilola Tuychiyevna	
Xorijiy davlatlarda boylik solig'i va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	1219
Ruziyev G'anisher Usarovich	
Yer fondi va undan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	1225
Xoshimova Sevara Baxromovna	
Iqtisodiy-ekologik tizimlarni boshqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning ilmiy asoslari	1229
Kuldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich	
Влияние финтех-услуг на финансовую инклюзию в сельских регионах узбекистана.....	1236
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Surxondaryo viloyati sanoat sohasining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari tahlili.....	1240
Kuvanchiyeva Mehriniso Davlyatgeldi qizi	
A critical evaluation of strategic management's role in promoting sustainable development in Uzbekistan	1245
Ismatova Mahliyo	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	O'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlari eksportini oshirishda zamonaviy infratuzilma va texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi.....	1251
	Akmal Bakhromov	
	Trends and reforms of corporate governance in state-owned enterprises.....	1257
	F.Djalilov	
	Переоценка долгосрочных активов в нефтегазовой промышленности и определение финансового результата от переоценки.....	1269
	Махкамова Саида Гайратова	
	Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari korxonalarini integratsiyalashuv jarayonlarini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish.....	1275
	Xojiev Ibroxim Ikramovich	
	Sug'urta kompaniyalari moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashning muhim shartlari.....	1280
	Allanazarova B.K.	
	P2P lending and crowdfunding as alternative sources of financing for small business in Uzbekistan.....	1286
	Abdurakhimova Dilara Karimovna	
	O'zbekistonda soliq nazoratining huquqiy va tashkiliy asoslarini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1290
	Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Oymatova Gulnur Mirjamolovna	
	Applications of hyperbolic geometry in physics and biology.....	1295
	Khaknazarova Khurshidabonu Kenjaevna, Otakulova Rukhshona Akram kizi	
	O'zbekiston temir yo'llari tizimining transformatsiyasi: modernizatsiya, raqamlashtirish va qayta tuzilish yo'nalishlari.....	1301
	Nasrullayev Nurbek Baxtiyarovich	
	The role of tourist product diversification in sustainable tourism development.....	1305
	Raxmonov Shuxrat Shavkatovich, Alimova Mashhura Toirxonovna	
Temiryo'l transporti turi tavsifi.....	1310	
Shodmonbekova Nodira Kamoljon qizi		
Namangan viloyatining turizm salohiyatini rivojlantirish istiqbollari: Hududiy raqobatbardoshlik va innovatsion yondashuvlar.....	1314	
Khusniddin Egamnazarov		
Kiberxavfsizlik: it infratuzilmasini himoya qilishning zamonaviy usullari.....	1321	
D. Sh. Usmanbayev		
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad bazasini tahlili.....	1325	
Qurbonov Nuriddin Ro'ziqulovich		
Развитие цифровых финансовых услуги в банковской системе Республики Узбекистан.....	1333	
Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамадаминовна		
Avariya rejimlarida kichik yuklamali elektr ta'minoti tizimlarining kabel izolyatsiyasi monitoringini avtomatlashtirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	1339	
Mirzoyev Narzulla Nuriddinovich, Mamatqulov Toyir Chorshanbiyevich		
Analysis of increasing the speed of information exchange between the control interface and execution mechanisms in emergency mode in intelligent systems.....	1346	
Azizbek Yusupbekov Nodirbekovich, Husniddin Esonov Mamarasul o'g'lu Assistant		
Sa'noat korxonalari va mexatron robotlarni optimal avtomatlashtirish va boshqarishda sun'iy intellektning ahamiyati.....	1351	
Karabayev Ibragim Turdiyevich, Esonov Husniddin Mamarasul o'g'li, Abdullayeva Saodat Mengbayevna, Mamatqulov Toir Chorshanbiyevich		
Korxonaning moliyaviy holatini baholashda zamonaviy tahlil uslublarining qo'llanilishi.....	1355	
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Suleymanova Asel Armanovna		
Xizmat ko'satish sohasida xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar va raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1360	
Mirzayeva Shirin Nodirovna		
Rekreatsiya turizmi va sog'lomlashtirish xizmatlari integratsiyasi.....	1365	
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna		
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatini rivojlantirishda ba'zi iqtisodiy yondashuvlarning nazariy jihatlari.....	1369	
Iskandarova D.B.		
Yashil (eko) investitsiyalarni tijorat banklari orqali moliyalashtirish.....	1373	
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna		

Improvement of inventory accounting audit based on international standards	1378
Ovlayev Suhrob Temur o'g'li, Yo'lchiyev Oybek Ulug'bek o'g'li, Normo'minova Dilorom Umar qizi, Avlayeva Oybachin Olim qizi	
Artificial intelligence systems for assessing creditworthiness	1382
Mardonova Durдона Yaxshiboy qizi	
B2B bozorini rivojlantirishda raqamli marketing texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni takomillashtirish	1387
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich	
Tech-driven growth and the economy of the future: brics-t in the society 5.0 paradigm	1395
Kaldibayev Nurlan Alimjanovich, Sagdullayeva Gulnora Botirovna, Durmanov, Akmal Shaimardanovich	
O'zbekistonda tabiiy resuslardan olinadigan rentaning yaimdagi ulushiga tanlab olingan o'zgaruvchilar ta'siri tahlili	1404
Tursunov Husnidin, Ibragimov Hasan	
O'zbekistonda fond bozorini tartibga solish	1412
Sultonov Sherali Nuraliyevich	
Public perception of the feasibility of introducing islamic banking in Uzbekistan: a consumer perspective	1418
Dr. Shamirova Surayyo Kabildjanovna	
Directions for implementing the innovative digital technologies in tourism	1425
Norchaev Asatullo Norbutaevich	
Возможности совершенствования практики финансирования инвестиционных проектов	1430
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Хакимов Хафизбек Хамза угли	
O'zbekistonda pochta aloqasi xizmatlarini ko'rsatishning transport-logistika jarayonini mintaqaviy darajada rivojlantirish yo'llarini ishlab chiqish	1436
Palvanbayev Umidbek O'ktam o'g'li	
Aksiyalar qiymatini baholashning nazariy asoslari	1440
Botirxo'ja Aziza Faxmuddin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni moliyalashtirishning rivojlanayotgan davlatlar amaliyoti tahlili	1444
Raimjanova Madina Asrarovna, Zokirova Feruza Farxod qizi	
Yashil loyihalarni davlat xususiy sheriklik asosida moliyalashtirish	1449
Zokirova Feruza Farxod qizi	
Факторы и риски, влияющие на оценку стоимости акции	1453
Батирхужа Азиза Фахмуддин кизи	
Финансовые риски в эпоху цифровой экономики: новые вызовы и способы управления	1458
Нуруллина Камила Рустамовна	
Tijorat banklarining yangi bank xizmatlarini iqtisodiy samaradorligi	1463
Rahmatov Temur Sotiboldiyevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish jarayonida ekologik innovatsiyalarning roli va amalga oshiruv mexanizmlari	1472
Ulichkina Lyudmila Ivanovna	
Эволюция профессиональных стандартов в республике узбекистан: от формирования к внедрению в сфере туризма	1478
Гольшева Елена Вячеславовна, Ивонина Наталья Викторовна	
Aligning uzbekistan's education reform with global best practices: the university of missouri as a model for systemic transformation	1485
Azamat Sulaymonov, Laylo Yakhshiboyeva	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarining investision faolligini ta'minlash masalalari	1489
Axmedov Shoymurod Azamat o'g'li	
Kichik biznes subyektlarining iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash masalasi	1493
Q.O.Tursunboyev	
Adoption of green economy mechanisms in the process of diversification of construction enterprises	1500
Yembergenova Aynur Aidosbayevna	
Nomoddiy aktivlar hisobini yuritish va audit jarayonlarini takomillashtirish yo'llari	1506
Rozmatova Umida Yuldashevna	
Raqamli moliya va uni sohaga joriy etish: innovatsion salohiyat	1512
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	

Влияние корпоративной культуры на инвестиционную стратегию промышленных предприятий.....	1527
Ёдгоров Сардорбек Самадович	
Jismoniy shaxslar kreditlarining bank portfeli sifatiga ta'siri: tahliliy yondashuv.....	1533
Sabirova Lobar Baxromovna	
Xo'jaligini soliqqa tortish mexanizmini samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1539
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
Methods of improving customs management in transforming the customs bodies into a corruption-free field	1544
Mirzaxmedova Dilafruz Farxatovna, Tukhtabaev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich	
Особенности цифровизации налоговой системы в узбекистане	1548
Юсупов Одил Омонович	
Qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalarda texnologik yangiliklarni joriy etish: muammolar va imkoniyatlar.....	1554
Ismailov Akmal axsudovich, G'ulomov Ilhom Akramovich	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini kreditlashda raqamli bank xizmatlaridan foydalanishning afzalliklari	1560
Madjitova Maftuna Kamiljon qizi	
Tadbirkorlikda tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari	1564
Ziyatova Sitara Baxtiyorovna	
Importance of media activity in negotiations.....	1569
Fariza Xoldarova	

IMPORTANCE OF MEDIA ACTIVITY IN NEGOTIATIONS

Fariza Xoldarova

TSUE-Pendidikan International educational joint program Senior teacher

Annotatsiya: This article states that in the context of the modern information revolution information technologies and public relations play an important role. For the first time in the history of mankind political culture is formed via electronic mass media. In addition, there have been analyzed the provision of the rule of law, the need to comply with it when conducting free negotiations in the information age, and that deviation from the law leads to negative consequences.

Kalit soʻzlar: cyberspace, negotiations, public relations, information technologies, the fourth power, mass media, virtual space, information exchange, political influence.

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy axborot inqilobi sharoitida axborot texnologiyalari va jamoatchilik bilan aloqalarning muhim oʻrin tutishi taʼkidlanadi. Insoniyat tarixida ilk bor siyosiy madaniyat elektron ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali shakllanmoqda. Shuningdek, axborot asrida erkin muzokaralarni oʻtkazishda qonun ustuvorligini taʼminlash, unga rioya qilish zarurati hamda qonundan chekinish salbiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi tahlil qilinadi.

Key words: kiber makon, muzokaralar, jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar, axborot texnologiyalari, toʻrtinchi hokimiyat, ommaviy axborot vositalari, virtual makon, axborot almashinuvi, siyosiy taʼsir.

Аннотация: В статье утверждается, что в условиях современной информационной революции информационные технологии и общественные связи играют важную роль. Впервые в истории человечества политическая культура формируется через электронные средства массовой информации. Кроме того, проанализированы обеспечение верховенства закона, необходимость его соблюдения при ведении свободных переговоров в информационную эпоху, а также то, что отклонение от закона приводит к негативным последствиям.

Ключевые слова: киберпространство, переговоры, общественные связи, информационные технологии, четвёртая власть, средства массовой информации, виртуальное пространство, информационный обмен, политическое влияние.

INTRODUCTION

Cyberspace is an important external environment for interactions between countries. At the same time, the Internet has become one of the important driving forces behind major changes in the world today that have not been seen in a century: the technological revolution has intensified changes in the relative power of major countries, helped the spread of online culture. The country is the main participant in international relations. Each phase of major scientific and technological innovation brings about major changes in the political structure of the country, and information technology is no exception. Unlike other sciences and technologies, the Internet brings not only a scientific and technical revolution, but also an information revolution. Information becomes an important strategic resource for the development of digital society, and it becomes an important resource in the political and economic spheres.

Mass media (mass media) is a means of conveying information to the masses and is one of the most characteristic features of modern civilization. With the help of mass media, people can get information about what is happening in the world in a short time. Mass media mainly include newspapers, magazines, radio and television. Mass communication means a message sent by a person or a group of people to a large audience through a transmission device (medium). Mass media is any medium for the transmission of mass

communications. Until our time, mass media has been defined and organized by eight mass media: books, newspapers, magazines and records, radio, film, television and the Internet.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In recent decades, the role of media in negotiations has gained increasing scholarly attention due to its profound influence on public perception, agenda-setting, and the strategic behavior of negotiating parties. Scholars such as Robert Entman emphasized the concept of “framing,” arguing that the media does not merely report events but actively shapes how conflicts and negotiations are understood by audiences. His framing theory highlights that media coverage can prioritize certain aspects of an issue while downplaying others, thus indirectly steering public opinion and influencing negotiation strategies.

Shanto Iyengar and Donald Kinder also showed through empirical research that media priming affects how individuals evaluate political actors and outcomes, which in turn can create pressure on negotiators, especially in international or high-stakes political dialogues. Furthermore, James Druckman examined how media cues affect the perceived legitimacy of negotiation processes, finding that negotiators adapt their communication styles depending on anticipated media exposure and audience reactions.

In conflict resolution research, William Zartman and I. William Zartman underscored that media visibility can be a double-edged sword. On the one hand, it increases transparency and international engagement; on the other, it may harden positions due to public scrutiny, making compromise more difficult. Similarly, Gadi Wolfsfeld emphasized the paradox of media in peace processes, noting that media tends to favor drama and conflict, which may undermine delicate negotiations aimed at achieving consensus.

Contemporary case studies, such as the Oslo Accords and climate negotiations under the UNFCCC framework, further demonstrate the media's dual role as both a facilitator and an obstacle. In summary, the literature suggests that media activity is not a neutral backdrop but a strategic component of modern negotiations that can shape narratives, alter power dynamics, and redefine the boundaries of acceptable compromise.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative content analysis method, focusing on case studies of international negotiations with high media involvement. Data were collected through systematic review of news reports, official press releases, and media statements from negotiation participants. These materials were analyzed using discourse analysis to identify framing patterns and media influence on negotiation dynamics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The first mass media are newspapers. The first newspaper. It was a handwritten pamphlet called «Events of the Day» published in Rome in 59 AD. Magazines appeared in the 18th century. The first magazines were compiled from newspapers and booksellers' catalogs. Radio and television appeared only in the last century.

The most popular mass media is television. Television brings images and sounds directly into people's homes. Thus, it is possible to watch what is happening in different parts of the world on TV without leaving the chair.

The most common mass media is radio. The reason for the widespread use of the radio is its compactness. This means you can easily carry the radio with you. People like to listen to the radio while relaxing, while driving, or while walking down the street. The main form of entertainment on the radio is music.

The cheapest media is a magazine. Magazines are not primarily concerned with covering daily and frequently changing events. They do an in-depth analysis of what happened in a certain period of time, for example, a week or a month. Magazines are designed for long-term use, so they are printed on thick and high-quality paper.

People often think of mass media as just news, but mass media also includes entertainment such as television shows, books, and movies. At the same time, it also includes education in nature, so educational programs are provided to the public in the form of public broadcasting stations. Political communication is spread through mass media, including propaganda. Thus, mass media is an important part of human society. Understanding media is central to understanding population and culture, and this explains why the field of media is so vast. Observing, reading and interacting with the media of any nation is the key to understanding what people think. For this reason, B.M. Hasanov said, «In Uzbekistan, as in other democratic countries, the mass media, especially recently, are not viewed as a means of communication that transmits information from person to person or to the public, but as a democratic institution that protects the interests of the state, society and individual. This requires taking into account the demands of media liberalization and the fact that it is an important institution of civil society. Such attention is primarily related to the need for free expression of opinions

and beliefs, political and ideological pluralism, freedom of speech and thought, and the need to additionally support other social values guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1]

A free press is an integral part of a democratic society. The mass media, as one of the powerful tools influencing all aspects of society's life, plays an important role in shaping public opinion, as well as determining the directions of development of socio-political processes. However, there is also a concept of «journalistic ethics» in the world. Every media outlet must adhere to the best principles of the press and be impartial and honest in reporting information to the public. Because «social and political freedom of mass media, i.e., consistent creation of economic and legal guarantees, further strengthening of their role in the development of the country, serves to immediately convey to the people the essence and importance of the comprehensive reforms that are being rationally implemented, and the successes being achieved in the way of building a new society of Uzbekistan[2]. «

Today, mass media is the most important tool for people to achieve change in the world. It is true that mass media is a means of entertainment, information and education as well as guidance. One of the moral obligations facing the media in Uzbekistan today is to follow the values and basic principles of the media.

The press of Uzbekistan is really acting as a messenger of advanced ideas. The mass media should not forget their responsibility to the society while putting all economic interests above them. But, unfortunately, it is impossible to see this in the mass media of some Western countries. Moral erosion, decline, departure from universally recognized moral and ethical standards and rules of professional etiquette, working based on the interests of political and economic circles have become a common norm even for a number of foreign mass media with historical traditions. Those societies that want to teach us a lesson about democracy, that are not lost in the dream of demanding democracy from us, should first of all see the light in their eyes.

Mass media is the most important tool for people to be aware of global changes. It is true that mass media serves as a tool for manipulating people as well as entertainment, source of information and education. «In the implementation of the concept of deepening democratic reforms and development of civil society in our country, we believe that citizens' self-governing bodies - neighborhoods, as well as non-governmental non-profit organizations, free and impartial mass media, will play an active role, as before. In the implementation of the important principle «from a strong state to a strong civil society», we first of all rely on the strength and capabilities of these social institutions[3].

One of the most important roles of mass media in modern societies is their position as intermediaries between political authorities and citizens. The mass media informs its audience about events in various spheres of politics, helps to shape public opinion, the ideological environment of individuals and their voting behavior. The main and sometimes the only source of information is communication through mass media, because it often conveys events that are outside the scope of direct experience of most members of society. At the same time, the mass media are not only an important source of information for citizens, they receive information from their products about the events happening on the political scene, the actions of the government, parliament or regional and local representative institutions, members of political parties, opinions and actions. Political communication plays an important role in this process.

Political communication is the process of forming and exchanging ideas between political actors, the media, and the public. It is concerned with the creation, distribution and influence of information in the mass media. It is a dominant element of the entire electoral and political process, including through which political information can be turned into political advantage. It is an interdisciplinary field that brings together a number of social sciences, from political science, sociology, psychology to media studies, economics and communication studies.

Communication and mass media are constantly evolving, mainly due to technological advancements. Since the beginning of the 21st century, the main role in political communication has been taken not by printed newspapers and party materials, but by internet media, social networks and television. With the advent of the Internet, the amount of data to be analyzed has increased significantly. Scientists and analysts of political subjects are moving to new computational methods to study political communication (they analyze the speeches of politicians, formal and informal conversations between the public, media output and their conception). In this field, the relationship between the three processes of political communication is intensively studied. Content is what the messages contain and what they are intended to convey to the recipient. Production is the way news is developed and communicated to the public in the mass media. Affect is the way messages are received and interpreted.

The elements of political communication are constantly changing. This change is mainly driven by the technological progress of the 21st century. Therefore, political actors are compelled to adapt to evolving techniques and technologies while attempting to use these developments to their advantage. Political organizations and politicians today not only use printed party materials and press conferences but also communicate with the

public directly through social networks such as Twitter and Facebook. Social media allows modern political actors to reach the public without intermediaries like traditional media outlets.

However, the downside of such direct communication is the ease with which false and populist messages can be spread to win elections. Political communication is an interactive process of information exchange among politicians, the media, and the public. This process operates in three directions: from governing institutions to citizens, horizontally between political actors, and upward from public opinion toward those in power. Political communication has always played a central role in electoral processes and policy-making.

Another well-known comparison that emerged in the 19th century relates to the classical threefold division of power legislative, executive, and judicial. In this context, the media has often been described as the “fourth estate,” acting as a mechanism that monitors all three branches. Just like each of the traditional powers, the media also carries responsibilities. For example, in established democracies, the executive branch is accountable to the legislature, just as a politician is accountable to their constituents; similarly, traditional media editors are accountable to their readers, listeners, or viewers.

The concept of the mass media as “guardians of democracy” includes the press, radio, television, and informational websites. These outlets not only provide news and updates about events in society but also serve as platforms for ideas that critically reflect politics and amplify societal concerns. Political accountability to the public is often ensured through the media, which plays a key role in exposing abuses of power, incompetence, or corruption. However, this watchdog function can be performed effectively only when the media is independent and operates within a legal framework that guarantees freedom of expression.

An essential aspect of the media’s influence in shaping public policy and opinion lies in its relationship with public sentiment. The media are perceived as carriers, collaborators, and representatives of public opinion. This concept generally symbolizes the set of views and evaluations expressed by members of society on particular issues and serves as an interpreter of collective interests.

On June 27, 2018 – the Day of Press and Mass Media Workers – the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted in his official address that significant progress had been made in strengthening the material and technical base of radio broadcasting, as well as in enhancing human resources. Most importantly, he emphasized that serious efforts had been undertaken to ensure diversity of opinions and perspectives in the press, which, as he put it, “is well known to all of you” [4].

When it comes to information, the responsibilities of states are more serious than those of ordinary citizens, as people tend to trust what authorities say. The freedom to seek information, which is integral to freedom of speech, includes the duty of states to actively disseminate content that serves the public interest and to foster diverse sources of information. This obligation is particularly crucial today, as individuals increasingly struggle to distinguish truth from falsehood.

Equally important is the responsibility of states and their representatives not to create or disseminate disinformation. As G.S. Mamatov rightly pointed out, although “information policy” is considered both national and universal, it is vital for society to establish a comprehensive system for receiving and distributing information. In the current era of globalization, distinguishing between accurate and fabricated information, ensuring that consumer rights are upheld, and preventing the spread of false information are all practical imperatives facing society. In this context, we may view state information systems as a kind of “data bank” that plays a strategic role in policy. For instance, platforms such as Norma, Pravo, and Lex.uz [5] serve as examples of such systems.

In modern societies, media coverage of politics or public interest issues cannot be separated from media coverage of political decision-making. The mass media has participated in the political direction of society’s life since its inception in its direction and form. This became evident when political trends and currents began to manifest themselves as social entities and political parties began to emerge.

Political parties are the main organizational structures through which different social groups promote their specific interests. Mass media are the center of attention of parties and their representatives, because citizens-voters form their perceptions about party activities more or less through mass media. Just as in ancient times orators tried to engage the audience with their point of view and purpose in their speeches at public gatherings, so do politicians today in the mass media. Therefore, the main issues that the parties are dealing with are their long- and short-term relations with the media and their strategies to influence, maintain or strengthen the media.

Currently, with exceptions, when the official affiliation of the mass media to political parties does not exist in practice, mass media try to act as translators of public opinion, more precisely, advocates of common interests, in relation to political parties. However, on the one hand, they cannot be clearly defined, and on the other hand, the form of mass media always sympathizes with a certain political trend, opinion, ideology, individual politician, etc. This is especially true of the private media sector. Public radio and television should be closest to this idea in terms of their functions. However, it is precisely these social institutions that politicians put a lot of pressure on in legal and illegal ways.

All mass media are in the field of political interest, because the difference in their technological nature allows politicians to use them for different ways of informing and persuading the public. But it is precisely this situation that requires the ability of politicians to comply with these special conditions of the media. On TV, a person with a sympathetic appearance who has mastered expressive abbreviations looks more reliable and convincing, on the radio the defect of visual appeal disappears, on the contrary, the importance of good articulation, logical structure of speech and pleasant tone disappears.

Politicians also seek to present themselves in new media. The Internet hosts the websites of individual political parties and politicians. Sometimes, for example, during elections or other campaigns, political parties spend a lot of money on billboards, leaflets and posters, paid advertisements, television and radio advertisements. The most recent discovery of the possibilities of mass media is the use of telephone and Internet mail for political campaigning. The ability to use modern digital technologies, which are able to present a «personal» message to a large number of users based on the organizational principle of the network, offers the appearance of an individual approach.

The above-mentioned features apply to the relationship between media, political parties and politicians, but as the oldest media, the press has come a long way with its partners and other media have only just joined it.

Today politics is done only through mass media. In them, the election campaign is held continuously, not once every four years. Politicians no longer intend to change the world, because the decisive processes here actually happen outside of them (at least in their opinion). In the 21st century, political activity is no longer about attracting the attention of citizens, but of viewers, listeners, and readers. It is not about people who consciously participate in democracy, who rationally evaluate the facts and proposals presented by politicians. Rather, it's about crowd control and anticipating cultural trends. Such a task requires different abilities, different skills than before. Being closer to the political scene in the media than in the cabinet pays off more. Because it is politics - even more powerful than before - that has become a theater, a kind of media reality show. Therefore, the winner is not only the one who can hypnotize the audience. The parties have already learned to live in the spirit of this order.

Narrative marketing succeeds. In the media, politics becomes a battle of constructed narratives, and election campaigns become narrative contests. It is no exaggeration to say that most political parties have long agreed that their agenda should be set by the mass media. Early morning television and news portals determine what people will discuss today, and politicians will have to adapt to the agenda. It is clear that they will be asked mainly (or only) about what journalists are currently interested in. All attempts at resistance, even holding press conferences on national issues, are futile.

Unable to change the situation, the politicians chose the way to carefully inspire the media, so that the journalists are convinced that they are the ones who set the agenda, when in fact the topic of the day is given to them by the party advisers.

The new information paradigm of international negotiations means that the effectiveness of the actions of the leaders participating in the negotiations largely depends on the information dominance in the virtual space. The modern concept of international negotiations requires the revision of outdated schemes and rules based on the latest information technologies and socio-cultural priorities. Today, good preparation for international negotiations means not only careful preparation of negotiating documents and development of strategy and tactics, but first of all, implementation of an excellent information campaign accompanying the negotiations in mass communication media. It is necessary to use new soft information technologies, to develop public relations with a subtle influence on public opinion in the world. Archimedes once said, «Give me a fulcrum and I will overturn the Earth.» Today, he would say, touching on the electrical means of our communication, «I will affect your ears and your nerves and your eyes and your brain and the world will turn at any speed and in any way that I want.»

The modern information revolution is bringing new principles and rules of political communication, changing the political image of the world. G'.S. Mamatov said, «The role of the mass media in our modern society should be as follows: providing information (that is, informing the population); mobilization and formation of public opinion; to support political literacy, education, political socialization of citizens; articulation of various interests in society; control state and local government bodies and express critical opinions on their activities; integration of policy subjects» [7].

The information is distributed in the space in an instant and it can be used by the political actors of different districts at the same time. As E. Giddens rightly noted, «we live in a world built on knowledge applied entirely by intuition, and in other words, we never believe that any element of it will not be revised [8]. «

From the point of view of political mobilization of society, information resources have the ability to cover everything and have an impact at the same time, which was almost impossible before the information revolution. The Internet is far more powerful than the combined power of the traditional three powers in terms of its power,

speed, and penetration. Political struggle is expanding day by day in the virtual information space and entering new, post-traditional virtual forms.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion, in the age of information, it is not appropriate to bring up various topics in the name of free discussion. It is required to ensure the rule of law, to follow it. However, it is surprising that among the non-democratic countries that do not respect the freedom of speech and opinion, regularly interfere and control its work, and are in the last fifty places of the rating table, there are also countries that are economically very strong. Because many people think that in order to have free speech and opinion, first of all, the economy should be strong and financial issues should be eliminated. The negative consequences of deviating from the law can be shown by the fact that in various countries of the world, under the guise of democracy, quarrels and wars arise during the organization of rallies and meetings, which lead to state development and chaos.

List of used literature:

1. Hasanov, B. M. In Uzbekistan: Citizenship of Society Formation and Development of Public Information Tools Activities Improvement. Political Sciences According to Philosophy, PhD Thesis Abstract. – p. 11.
2. Hasanov, B. M. Improving the Activities of Mass Media in the Formation and Development of Civil Society in Uzbekistan. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Political Sciences. – p. 12.
3. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. We Will Resolutely Continue Our Path of National Development and Raise It to a New Level. Vol. I. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. – p. 141.
4. Xalq so'zi Newspaper, June 28, 2018.
5. Mamatov, G'. S. Harmony of Public Control and State Information Policy in the Information Society (In the Case of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Political Sciences According to Philosophy, PhD Dissertation Abstract. – Tashkent, 2020. – p. 15.
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 05.10.2018 «On Measures to Further Strengthen Executive Discipline in State Bodies and Organizations».
7. Mamatov, G'. S. Harmony of Public Control and State Information Policy in the Information Society (In the Case of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Political Sciences According to Philosophy, PhD Dissertation Abstract. – Tashkent, 2020. – p. 18.
8. Giddens, A. Postindustrial Modernity. In Novaya Postindustrialnaya Volna na Zapade: Anthology. Moscow, 1999. – p. 106.
9. Giddens, E. Postmodernity. In Novaya Postindustrialnaya Volna na Zapade: Anthology. Moscow, 1999. – p. 106.
10. Uzbekistan Republic President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's Speech at the 72nd Session of the United Nations General Assembly, September 19, 2017. [Electronic source] www.uza.uz
11. Webster, D. Creation of Free and Independent Media. Freedom Treatise, No. 1, p. 3.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 5

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
